

Thinking Without Phenomenal Character: How are Artificial Intelligence, Cognitive Phenomenology, and Extended Cognition Related?

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Abstract—This paper is intended to provide a rough overview of the relationship between artificial intelligence and cognitive phenomenology, in addition to extended cognition. Both cognitive states and phenomenal states are possible states had by humans, animals, and perhaps other objects, systems, or entities; but cognitive states and phenomenal states are distinguishable. On some views, machines merely need to act sufficiently intelligently to be intelligent, but on some stronger views, machines must be phenomenally conscious to be thinking, intelligent creatures. In a similar vein to the latter view of artificial intelligence, many varieties of cognitive phenomenology maintain that thinking requires conscious experience, which (assuming thinking and intelligence are coextensive) entails machines must be phenomenally conscious to think or to be intelligent. But such views about cognitive phenomenology unnecessarily complicate the relationship between cognition and phenomenal character, and the very nature of cognitive states. Moreover, according to extended accounts of cognition, cognitive states and phenomenal states may bear no necessary connection at all. As I will argue, it is possible and ontologically simpler to explain thought without appealing to proprietary or any other phenomenal character. On this ontologically simpler view of cognition, a machine can theoretically be a thinking thing without being in a phenomenal state.

Index Terms—artificial, intelligence, cognitive, phenomenology, extended

I. INTRODUCTION

Must a machine experience phenomenal character of cognition, or phenomenal states at all, to be intelligent? On some accounts, such as a moderate view of cognitive phenomenology, to be a thinking thing or an intelligent being, an agent must experience phenomenal character, and not just any kind, but a kind proprietary to and necessary for thought. Assuming intelligence and thinking go hand-in-hand, such positive views about cognitive phenomenology entail that to be intelligent, a machine must also experience phenomenal character, entailing a strong view about artificial intelligence (AI).

On the other hand, a negative position about cognitive phenomenology leaves open the possibility that a thinking thing would not need to be in a phenomenal state in order

to think or be intelligent. Such negative views about the relationship between phenomenal character and cognition are metaphysically simpler than the positive claims about cognitive phenomenology and just as explanatorily powerful, so there is reason to endorse such negative views. Moreover, the extended cognition thesis, according to which cognitive states are distributed, suggests that there are already existing cognitive systems in which the whole and at least some of the parts do not experience phenomenal character. This suggests that a thinking thing does not need to experience phenomenal character to think, so a machine could be intelligent without experiencing phenomenal character.

This relationship between cognitive phenomenology, extended cognition, and artificial intelligence has until now not been evaluated in detail, but this is the project undertaken in this paper. After arguing from a negative view about cognitive phenomenology that Strong AI mistakenly assigns phenomenal character a role in cognitive states, this paper more briefly explores how including relevant aspects of an agent's environment in the relevant cognitive states implies AI is already playing a significant role in cognition.

II. STRONG ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Intelligence in humans is typically understood as requiring that being to think, and the same can be said for non-human intelligence, both purely theoretical and actual, among all possible intelligent or thinking things. For example, problem solving including that which involves the use of tools is typically seen as requiring thought and reflecting intelligent behavior, such as an animal making and using a tool specifically to do something like drink water is an indication that the being performing that behavior is intelligent [1]. Such intelligent behavior has been found in not just primates, but also in other kinds of animals like corvids [2], and intelligence in some senses may be best understood as being had in varying degrees [3]. However, what it would take for a creature such as a machine to be intelligent is a matter of some controversy, and there are many different ways of understanding intelligence in the field of AI [4].

Specific examples of technology considered AI currently used includes software which recognizes patterns, such as faces of individual people [5]; software which produces works of so-called “art” [6]; and self-driving automobiles capable of avoiding collisions and otherwise helping those riding in them arrive safely at their intended destinations [7]. An important development in AI has been machine learning, whereby machines ‘learn’ from data without programming. Artificial neural networks and support vector machines are two varieties of machine learning models through which the performance of a machine improves with respect to some function or task over time. Bisgin et al. [8], for example, showed that SVM and ANN machine learning models allowed for accurate genus identification with potentially food-contaminating beetles, and the relevant systems were able to predict the genus of various kinds of beetles with a high degree of accuracy [8]. Autonomous robot teams are able to complete search-and-rescue missions and save human lives [9]. However, these examples of AI are relatively domain-narrow, and do not meet the minimum requirements for a machine on its own to be genuinely intelligent by most common standards in AI.

There are multiple views about what is required for a machine to actually be intelligent, and what the relevant goal(s) of the field of AI are when it comes to creating an intelligent machine. One common way of demarcating the various relevant views is to understand the goals of the field of AI in terms of a machine’s actions or behavior, on the one hand, and its mental states or thinking process(es), on the other hand [4]. The former, Weak AI, establishes a requirement that a machine act or behave in a way that seems on a par with a rational human or other intelligent agent, such as responding appropriately to a conversation with a person. Alan Turing [10] offers a way of determining whether a machine is intelligent by proposing an imitation game, and testing whether a subject can distinguish between the answers of a machine and the answers of a human with average cognitive capacities to questions posed by a third party. However, it is not clear to everyone interested in AI that merely acting intelligently or passing some such Turing Test means that the relevant machine is in fact intelligent.

An alternative to the Weak AI view is that AI aims to produce a machine that thinks like humans or other intelligent animals, objects, or systems. This means that a machine must actually think like a human (or other intelligent agent) to genuinely be intelligent, and not merely behave intelligently or simulate intelligence. According to at least some versions of Strong AI, this missing crucial ‘ingredient’ is phenomenal character, and a machine must be able to experience phenomenal character to be an intelligent agent (A1). Although intentionality rather than phenomenality may have been John Searle’s [11] original focus, his Chinese Room Argument can be taken to support an analogous conclusion about phenomenal states as well. According to such an interpretation, consciousness is required for thought and does not just emerge from a machine, even if it happens to be running the right input-output program or functioning in a certain way. Importantly, others

disagree that machines cannot be so phenomenally conscious [12], [13].

According to such Strong AI views, consciousness or the experience of phenomenal character is at least implicitly assumed to be necessary for intelligence in machines. If this position is accurate, merely passing a Turing Test would not indicate whether the would-be thinking thing is in any phenomenally conscious mental state, or more importantly for the purposes of AI, whether they are actually intelligent. Other variations of Strong AI are possible, including views which focus on intentionality rather than phenomenal character, such as Searle’s own view in his original [11] paper on artificial minds. However, the present paper is concerned specifically with the variations of Strong AI according to which a system or entity cannot be intelligent without being conscious, in the sense of experiencing phenomenal states. That is, the present paper is focused on Strong AI views according to which artificial consciousness is necessary for artificial intelligence, and the relationship of such a view with the cognitive phenomenology debate. Whether artificial consciousness matters more generally has been addressed previously by Hildt [14]. While it is clear that consciousness often plays a role when deciding whether entities should count as moral patients, it is not clear whether consciousness is necessary for intelligence, or whether the field of AI should be understood as having the creation of artificial consciousness as one of its goals. After this topic has been examined, I will explain how this connects to intentionality-based views of cognition.

III. COGNITIVE PHENOMENOLOGY

There is another debate related to the debate between Strong AI and Weak AI, although the relationship between these two debates has been hitherto largely unexplored, and this second debate is about the phenomenal character or subjective feeling of occurrent thought or cognition. Many kinds of phenomenal states are familiar to the majority of people, such as those associated with the five basic human senses; what it is like to see the color blue or to hear a tree hit the ground, for example, are kinds of phenomenal character which many people have experience with. There are other such phenomenal states, like those associated with proprioception. There are other kinds of phenomenal states which are commonly taken to exist, but with which humans generally do not have first-hand experience, such as the feeling of being a bat using echolocation [15]. But there is another kind of phenomenal character for which its very existence is controversial for a variety of relevant experts, and that is the alleged proprietary phenomenal character of thought.

There are different ways to understand the cognitive phenomenology debate, but elsewhere [16] I argue that cognitive phenomenology should be understood as focusing on issues of metaphysical necessity. For example, consider the talk of fundamental, essential, intrinsic properties in the following quotes from various authors about the debate (emphasis added):

The disagreement surrounding conscious thought . . . concerns its *fundamental* nature.

Bayne and Montague [17], page 1

The intentional content of a conscious thought is like the sensational content of a conscious pain—they are the states they are not because of their relational properties, but because of their *intrinsic* phenomenal nature.

Pitt [18], page 141

Conscious thought is an essentially phenomenological or experiential phenomenon, just as perceptual experience and emotional experience are *essentially* phenomenological-experiential phenomena.

Montague [19], page 174

Each of these excerpts is concerned with the metaphysical nature of thought and its metaphysical relationship with phenomenal character. This interpretation of the debate is the best account [16], as the concern is obviously not just with some contingent relationship between phenomenal states and thoughts, which would be too weak. On the other hand, some may take the cognitive phenomenology debate to be concerned with nomological necessity. Robinson, for example, suggested that it is a “nontrivial empirical” issue [20] whether subvocalization is necessary for thought. If advocates of moderate or strong cognitive phenomenology cannot show that proprietary (or individuating) phenomenal character is *metaphysically* necessary for an occurrent thought due to the metaphysical nature of cognition, the best available option is to argue that phenomenal character is *nomologically* necessary for thought. However, this would require some substantive nomological connection between phenomenal character and occurrent thoughts, and it is not clear that any argument for this conclusion could avoid issues of question-begging. Moreover, this kind of necessity would fail to address the essential nature of any of the relevant mental states.

The debate about cognitive phenomenology is also not generally concerned with the logical or conceptual relationship between phenomenal states and thought, which would be too strong. Conceptual necessity is not of central importance, as nothing about the concept of “thought” necessitates nonsensory phenomenal character. In fact, according to Mendelovici, intentional states (including cognitive states) and phenomenal states are “conceptually distinct” [21]. Rather, the best account of the cognitive phenomenology debate is that the focus is on the metaphysical relationship between phenomenal and cognitive states. I break the possible views about metaphysical necessity down into three main possible positive views, and the standard negative view which denies the moderate and strong variations. Since such an interpretation of the debate is about the metaphysical nature and relationships of cognitive states in general, it also presumably applies to thought and intelligence within machines.

The weakest of the positive views, *Phenomenal Cognitive Phenomenology*, suggests that there is a phenomenal state such that anyone or anything experiencing that phenomenal character must be thinking some thought. However, this leaves open the possibility that it is possible to think without any

such kind of phenomenal character, which many proponents of cognitive phenomenology (such as Pitt [22]) wish to deny.

Moderate Cognitive Phenomenology is the view that there is some proprietary phenomenal character of thought necessary to think a thought, proprietary in the sense that the states in question are only possibly experienced while thinking. This is consistent with there being some general phenomenal character of understanding, which is necessary for any agent to be thinking, which is the same phenomenal character for anyone thinking any thought. Moderate Cognitive Phenomenology also leaves open the possibility that there is a phenomenal character of, for example, thinking ‘ $1+1=2$ ’ on the one hand and deliberating whether to choose one of two possible answers on a biology test, on the other hand. In this hypothetical scenario consistent with Moderate Cognitive Phenomenology, these two kinds of phenomenal character are distinguishable, and the difference is not reducible to differences in phenomenal character possibly had in non-cognitive states.

Strong Cognitive Phenomenology is an even stronger claim about cognitive phenomenal character, according to which there is a unique phenomenal character required to think any given thought. That is, an agent thinking the thought that ‘ $1+1=2$ ’ is experiencing a different phenomenal character from when thinking ‘Most birds fly’, and this phenomenal character is in turn different from any other distinct thought. According to such views, it is impossible to be thinking a thought without experiencing the phenomenal character unique to that thought (for example, see Pitt [22], [18]). Strong Cognitive Phenomenology entails Moderate Cognitive Phenomenology, as it requires phenomenal character unique to each thought, which would mean that there is a set of phenomenal character instances for which it is impossible to be in them without thinking.

Although there are various ways of spelling out the different positive views about cognitive phenomenology, a negative view about cognitive phenomenology which denies that proprietary phenomenal character is necessary for thought is overall the preferable view to take because it requires holding fewer speculative commitments about any necessary relationship between cognition and phenomenal character. A view in this general camp is defended by Carruthers and Veillet [23], where they focus specifically on a constitutive relation. In general, views with equal explanatory power with fewer speculative metaphysical or ontological commitments are preferable, and negative views about the relationship between cognition and phenomenal character arguably do just that compared to positive views about cognitive phenomenology.

An agent can think, and can know what they are thinking just by virtue of being in this mental state, and this explanation need not appeal to any sort of phenomenal character proprietary to thought or necessary relationships between thought and phenomenal character ([24], [25]). So negative views about cognitive phenomenology are ontologically simpler and explanatorily equivalent, and when there are no need for commitments to metaphysical relationships or entities of the

sort proposed by positive views about cognitive phenomenology, we ought not endorse such claims (for more general remarks not specific to the cognitive phenomenology debate, see Schaffer [26]). Specifically, my argument in Parks [16] is that we ought to endorse the negative view about cognitive phenomenology on the grounds that it fares better in terms of explanatory virtues, informed by a view of explanatory virtues developed by Keas [27], and it goes as follows:

A. Argument for a Negative View about Cognitive Phenomenology

- 1) Positive and negative views about cognitive phenomenology are largely equivalent when it comes to their explanatory virtues, including evidential, diachronic, and coherential virtues.
- 2) Positive and negative views about cognitive phenomenology are not equivalent when it comes to their ontological commitments; negative views about cognitive phenomenology are at an advantage here [because such negative views are metaphysically simpler in that they are committed to fewer metaphysically necessary relationships].
- 3) If two theories are equivalent with respect to their evidential, diachronic, and coherential virtues but one fares better with respect to metaphysical commitments, we ought to endorse that view.
- 4) We ought to endorse a negative view about cognitive phenomenology.

Although opponents might argue that positive views about cognitive phenomenology is potentially simpler in that, at least on some versions, these states are identical and so the number of entities might be said to be reduced. However, then a complicated story is owed about how these two seemingly distinct states are actually the same, and since there is no obviously correct answer, this complicates their view. Opponents may also argue that their positive views about cognitive phenomenology have some other benefit not shared by negative views, but this choice may to some extent ultimately be a matter of aesthetics. For now, it suffices to say that there is reason to think negative views about cognitive phenomenology are preferable, although this position is controversial.

IV. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN COGNITIVE PHENOMENOLOGY AND STRONG AI

Before discussing the relationship between cognitive phenomenology and AI, one assumption must be explicitly made and defended: any thinking thing is an intelligent thing (A2). This connection between thinking and intelligence is both intuitive and also explicitly discussed in print. For example, Sparrow and Davis say cognition and intelligence “are often considered synonymous” [28], and Rindermann, Becker, and Coyle say “cognitive ability is understood as the ability to think (intelligence)” [29]. Under the assumption that thinking and intelligence are co-extensive, different moderate and strong views about cognitive phenomenology entail different claims about AI.

Phenomenal Cognitive Phenomenology, according to which there is a special phenomenal character only possibly had when thinking some thoughts, does not entail anything about the debate between Strong AI and Weak AI. This is because Phenomenal Cognitive Phenomenology does not say anything about the nature of thought or thinking things, but rather, only that it is possible that some phenomenal character can only be had while thinking. This does not entail anything about whether or not machines must be conscious or phenomenally aware of anything to be thinking, intelligent creatures, so Phenomenal Cognitive Phenomenology is largely irrelevant to the debate about Strong AI.

On the other hand, according to Moderate Cognitive Phenomenology, experience of phenomenal character proprietary to thought is necessary for a thing to be thinking. On this view, to be intelligent, any potential case of AI must experience phenomenal character (in keeping with the claims of Strong AI), and not just any kind, but specifically proprietary to and necessary for thought. Indeed, requiring machines to experience conscious thought to be really intelligent seems to suggest that phenomenal character is necessary for a thing to think.

Significantly, Strong Cognitive Phenomenology entails an even stronger view about AI, specifically, that a machine would need to be in a different cognitive phenomenal state for each distinct thought to actually think, and not merely mimic intelligence. Thus, both Moderate Cognitive Phenomenology and Strong Cognitive Phenomenology suggest that phenomenal experience is necessary for thought, so on these views, intelligence requires phenomenal character. This in turn entails Strong AI, since any genuine case of AI must experience such phenomenal states to think or be intelligent.

On the other hand, if a negative view about cognitive phenomenology is true, machines need not experience phenomenal character to genuinely be thinking. This would be consistent with a weaker variation of Strong AI, which I will call Strong AI*, according to which a machine can think, like a human or other intelligent agent, without being in a phenomenal state; no necessary relationship between cognition and phenomenal character is assumed on this view.

In theory, according to a negative view about cognitive phenomenology, since thinking arguably does not require the thinker to experience any phenomenal character, machines can be intelligent thinking entities, possibly without having phenomenal experience at all. Given that a negative view of cognitive phenomenology does not make any positive claims about the relationship between thought and phenomenal states, it leaves open the possibility that a creature can think without phenomenal character, proprietary to thought or otherwise. If any phenomenal character would be necessary to be in a cognitive state, the most likely candidate would be cognitive phenomenal character, barring some additional relationship between non-cognitive phenomenal character and cognitive states. Thus, being in a phenomenal state is not necessary for any thing to be thinking (A3) is one reasonable negative view about the relationship between cognition and phenomenal

states.

Moreover, unrelated to the cognitive phenomenology debate, a great deal of cognition and information processing takes place below the level of conscious experience, which gives even more reason to distinguish the issue of whether a machine is intelligent to whether it is capable of being in a phenomenal state. Such considerations provide even more reason to think that whether or not a machine experiences phenomenal character is an issue distinct from whether or not a machine is intelligent.

The argument is as follows:

A. *Argument Against Strong AI*

If Strong AI is true, then a machine must be able to experience phenomenal character to be intelligent. (A1)

Any thinking thing is an intelligent thing. (A2)

Being in a phenomenal state is not necessary for any thing to be thinking. (A3)

Therefore, it is not the case that a machine must experience phenomenal character to think. (by 3)

Therefore, it is not the case that a machine must be able to experience phenomenal character to be intelligent. (by 2,4)

Therefore, Strong AI is not true. (by 1, 5)

B. *Objections and Replies*

Since this argument is valid, it would be necessary to defend Strong AI by rejecting the truth of one or more of the claims out of A1 (about Strong AI), A2 (about the relationship between thinking and intelligence), and A3 (the denial of any significant sort of necessity relationship between phenomenality and cognition). I will consider each of these possibilities in turn.

1) *Assumption A1*: It is possible for defenders of Strong AI to reject my characterization of Strong AI. It is possible the claims made here do not apply to at least some of the folks who take themselves to be in the Strong AI debate. But if that is the case, then it is up to the opponent to explicitly make clear where my interpretation falls short and why another interpretation is better. This would mean shifting the focus of Strong AI away from phenomenal consciousness and onto something different. Moreover, to the extent that my characterization of Strong AI is correct, then the argument goes through at this point.

2) *Assumption A2*: It is also possible to reject A2, a proposed and intuitive connection between thought and intelligence. However, it is unclear what would make a creature intelligent if not thinking, but more importantly, it does seem to be the case that all agents who are thinking are also intelligent, for all intents and purposes relevant to this paper. Again, this claim about the relationship between thought and intelligence is intuitive, and they are widely considered “synonymous” and “understood” in terms of each other [28], [29]. So, to reject this premise of the argument, an opponent must offer good reason to think the notions of thought and intelligence at issue are not so closely related.

3) *Assumption A3*: Lastly, it is possible to reject A3, a negative view about the relationship between cognitive states and phenomenal states. This seems to be the most promising option for Strong AI defenders to take, and as Picard [13] notes, there is strong evidence suggesting that phenomenal states such as emotions play a role in at least many cases of human cognition. However, there is no reason to think that this relationship is metaphysically necessary, or that cognition could not possibly happen without phenomenal character. As I argued previously, a negative view about the relationship between cognition and phenomenal character requires commitments to fewer metaphysical relationships, and is just as explanatorily powerful as a positive view about cognitive phenomenology. So all things considered, a negative view seems to be the preferable view to take. Thus, if a defender of Strong AI wants to reject A3, they will need to argue, in a non-circular manner, that phenomenal character (of any variety) is actually necessary for thought.

C. *Extended Cognition and A3*

Although the relationship between extended cognition and AI cannot receive the full treatment it deserves in this paper, I will outline some of the ways views about extended cognition and AI are related. The view that an existing system can have cognitive states or intelligence without the entire system possessing phenomenal character provides positive reason to deny that phenomenal character is necessary for thought. Such a view is required for an extended account of cognition according to which cognitive states are distributed across various subsystems, where phenomenal character is not always experienced by the relevant system-in-a-cognitive-state considered as a whole. In their paper ‘The Extended Mind,’ Clark and Chalmers [30] argue that cognition is not necessarily internal to an agent, but rather, can be distributed to include some relevant aspects of the environment; there’s no reason to limit cognitive processes to the physical space and goings-on within the skull. Just as cognition is distributed across a notebook and an agent with an impaired memory relying on said notebook to navigate their environment, it can also be distributed across computers and agents. For example, a human using a mouse or a hypothetical neural implant to manipulate an image on the computer’s monitor each represents a case of extended cognition. While I will not provide any original or extensive defense of the extended cognition thesis, such arguments are available elsewhere [30].

Assuming phenomenal character is not being experienced by the entire system including both the agent and their computer, the extended cognition thesis allows for genuine cases of cognitive states without being in a phenomenal state. In fact, Clark and Chalmers pose the question, “why should the nature of an associated phenomenology make a difference to the status of a belief?” [30] with the implied answer presumably being that associated phenomenology makes no difference. Thus, there is no obvious necessary connection between cognition and phenomenal states on such extended cognition views, which can explain how AI might play an

increasingly significant role in a cognitive system which lacks phenomenal character. This is the case even if such machines considered apart from their environment would not be considered genuinely intelligent at present, which may change given future possible developments.

However, if one takes seriously the view that cognition is extended, perhaps evaluation of the intelligence of a system should not be considered in isolation of its environment, including machines and humans interacting with them. This is not to say that all cognition is distributed or extended, but rather, that in some cases it can be, perhaps including human-robot teams [31]. Adopting such a broader view of cognition means that other modern AI technologies such as beetle-identifying AI [8] discussed in Section II may count as subsystems of more complex intelligent systems or states, systems which also often involve users or possibly developers as components. The system as a whole is not phenomenally conscious, while plausibly counting as a case of a cognitive state distributed across the human-AI team, providing grounds on which to defend A3.

1) *Objections and Replies:* It is possible for an opponent to take issue with the claim that cognition is extended. For example, Smart [32] considers that, among other possible issues, problems for views about extended cognition include accounting for what kinds of states or systems count as cognitive and reasons to think that entities such as computers are part of any cognitive state or system.

However, none of the issues faced by views like the extended cognition thesis are insurmountable, or else are shared in common with other views about cognition. For example, the determining what counts as a cognitive state or system is an issue shared by all views about cognition and intelligence, but this 'issue' may not be as problematic as may *prima facie* be the case. There are reasons not to strive for a specific account of what counts as a cognitive state or an intelligent system, including that such an account is unattainable as cognition involves a variety of different kinds of processes and does not involve a natural kind [33]. The same could be said of intelligence.

While different notions of cognitive states and intelligence may be an underlying issue contributing toward some of the controversies in the debates about cognitive phenomenology and Strong AI, it is clear that a singular point of contention within each of the debates is whether cognition or intelligence can be had without phenomenal character or conscious experience, and it is this point which I am defending in this paper.

Some in the cognitive phenomenology debate in particular maintain that the metaphysical natures of and relationships between cognition and phenomenal character maintain that truths about such matters are introspectively accessible, and my views about them are wrong. However, introspection produces conflicting results about the more general relationship between phenomenal character and cognition. Moreover, the view that the metaphysical relationship between thought and phenomenal character is knowable through introspection is itself dubious, especially when epistemic expert peers have

conflicting introspective results [34]. While another explanation is that some of the folks engaging with each other within these debates have different notions of cognition in mind, I acknowledge that such is the case within these kinds of debates, but exploring this in any further detail is beyond the scope of the present paper.

With respect to cognition within the extended cognition debate, none of the objections against the extended cognition thesis refute it or give any reason to adopt a narrower account of cognition over a broader one. Just as a person's blood filtration processes can be partially done with artificial subsystems (e.g., dialysis), so can cognitive processes be done with different sorts of artificial subsystems; there is no reason given to think that cognition must be restricted to boundaries stopping at the edge of a person's body. Even if the artificial subsystem in question is not considered to be a fully-fledged cognitive system on its own, such subsystems can still play a significant role in the relevant complete cognitive systems which themselves may be considered intelligent, perhaps more so than any of their components individually. Insofar as a broader view of cognition provides a better understanding of the state in question, as is the case with a broader view of blood filtration given that it can be performed partially externally, the extended cognition thesis seems to be on solid ground. But views about extended cognition, like views about AI and cognitive phenomenology, ultimately relies on controversial assumptions about the metaphysical nature of the relevant states not shared by opponents.

D. Discussion

It is important to note that even if the Argument Against Strong AI is sound, which opponents will deny, this would not imply that Weak AI is true, as to be a thinking thing may require something other than phenomenal consciousness or passing a Turing Test. The purpose of this paper is not to defend Weak AI, but rather, to show that at least some variations of Strong AI are misguided insofar as they are focused on the significance of phenomenal character when it comes to intelligence without offering any reason to think that such phenomenal character is in fact necessary for thought or intelligence, when that is the very point at issue.

Being in the right sort of state for a machine to be considered thinking or intelligent does not obviously require the experience of any sort of phenomenal character. Lacking reasons to endorse some more complicated view with the same explanatory power, it is simpler to suppose cognitive states and phenomenal character are not necessarily connected, a view also supported by considerations stemming from extended cognition views. Endorsing both a negative view about the relationship between cognition and phenomenal character along with the view that thinking things are intelligent suggests Strong AI is misguided, although some versions of Strong AI* may be on more solid ground if they do not require phenomenal consciousness for an entity to be intelligence.

Consider, for example, the Strong AI* view that intentionality is necessary for cognition and intelligence [11]. Short of

endorsing some complicated view about the relationship between phenomenal and intentional states, this alternative view avoids the complications which arise from trying to justify positing any metaphysically necessary relationships between what appear to be fundamentally different kinds of states, i.e., phenomenal and cognitive states. However, proponents of views like the Phenomenal Intentionality Thesis (PIT) or any other which entail metaphysically necessary relationships between phenomenal and intentional states (including cognitive states) are open to the same line of arguments as I developed in section III against positive views about cognitive phenomenology [16].

Regardless of whether opponents agree with the truth of the premises in my argument against Strong AI, it remains the case that views about the relationship between phenomenal states and cognitive states, central to A3, are at the heart of both the cognitive phenomenology debate and intuitions about Strong AI. Specifically, maintaining a positive view about cognitive phenomenology according to which phenomenal character of a certain sort is necessary for thought entails that A3 is false and (along with a couple of additional not implausible assumptions) that Strong AI is true. While this is possibly an internally consistent view about cognition and phenomenal character to hold, as I argued in Section III, it is my own view that this position is unnecessarily complicated, and the simpler alternative is preferable for this reason. The implications of taking such a position include endorsing beliefs relevant to debates about personhood, agency, and other philosophical issues, which the author intends to explore in detail in future research.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In terms of implications for the future of the field of AI, the conclusions of this paper suggest that AI need not aim toward producing phenomenally conscious creatures to produce a genuinely intelligent machine or system. To be clear, there may yet be something more required than merely acting intelligently in some domain(s) for a machine to be actually intelligent in the sense of thinking like a human or other relatively rational agent, but whether that includes phenomenal consciousness is a controversial issue, and my own (I believe, simpler) view is that cognition and intelligence are possible without phenomenal consciousness.

The Argument Against Strong AI leaves open the possibility that some current or future machine can experience phenomenal character, in line with views like that of Buccella and Springle [35]. However, others like Searle [36] argue machines cannot develop this capacity. But the alleged possibility of machines developing phenomenal consciousness appears to stem from what is currently a large gap between cognitive states of any kind and phenomenal states, it is not clear whether it will ever actually be closed. This is this very same gap which motivates A3.

This paper is intended to provide a rough overview of the relationship between the cognitive phenomenology debate and AI, and explain how the disagreement within each of

the debates depends on differences in opinion about the relationship between intelligence or cognition, on the one hand, and phenomenal character or conscious experience, on the other hand. I also defend a particular account, namely, a negative view about the relationship between cognition and phenomenal character, and that Strong AI is false. Many varieties of cognitive phenomenology suggest that thinking requires conscious experience, which entails machines must be phenomenally conscious to think or to be intelligent. Positive views about cognitive phenomenology unnecessarily complicate the relationship between cognition and phenomenal character, and the very nature of cognitive states. Moreover, according to some extended accounts of cognition, cognitive states and phenomenal states are distinguishable and bear no necessary connection. As I have previously clarified, it is possible and ontologically simpler to explain thought without appealing to proprietary or any other phenomenal character. On this ontologically simpler view of cognition, Strong AI*, a machine can theoretically be a thinking thing without being in a phenomenal state.

Both cognitive states and phenomenal states are possible states had by humans and other animals, and possibly other systems, objects, and entities, but these cognitive and phenomenal states are distinguishable. There is little to no reason to insist that machines be phenomenally conscious to be thinking, intelligent creatures on their own, or be phenomenally conscious to play a role in intelligent extended cognitive systems. So, until a great deal of progress has been made toward closing the gap between phenomenal states and cognitive states, the Strong AI claim that machines are intelligent only if they experience phenomenal states seems to rely upon an unnecessarily complicated view of the relationship between phenomenal states and cognitive states.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Lapuente, T. C. Hicks, and K. E. Linsenmair, "Fluid dipping technology of chimpanzees in comoe national park, ivory coast," *American Journal of Primatology*, vol. 79, no. 5, p. e22628, 2017.

- [2] N. J. Emery and N. S. Clayton, "The mentality of crows: convergent evolution of intelligence in corvids and apes," *science*, vol. 306, no. 5703, pp. 1903–1907, 2004.
- [3] P. Carruthers *et al.*, "Invertebrate concepts confront the generality constraint (and win)," *The philosophy of animal minds*, pp. 89–107, 2009.
- [4] S. J. Russell, *Artificial intelligence a modern approach*. Pearson Education, Inc., 2010.
- [5] M. Smith and S. Miller, "The ethical application of biometric facial recognition technology," *Ai & Society*, pp. 1–9, 2022.
- [6] J. V. Pavlik, "Collaborating with chatgpt: Considering the implications of generative artificial intelligence for journalism and media education," *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, p. 10776958221149577, 2023.
- [7] E. Guizzo, "How google's self-driving car works," *IEEE Spectrum Online*, vol. 18, no. 7, pp. 1132–1141, 2011.
- [8] H. Bisgin, T. Bera, H. Ding, H. G. Semey, L. Wu, Z. Liu, A. E. Barnes, D. A. Langley, M. Pava-Ripoll, H. J. Vyas *et al.*, "Comparing svm and ann based machine learning methods for species identification of food contaminating beetles," *Scientific reports*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2018.
- [9] G. A. Cardona and J. M. Calderon, "Robot swarm navigation and victim detection using rendezvous consensus in search and rescue operations," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 8, p. 1702, 2019.
- [10] A. M. Turing, "Computing machinery and intelligence (1950)," *The Essential Turing: the Ideas That Gave Birth to the Computer Age*, pp. 433–464, 2012.
- [11] J. R. Searle, "Minds, brains, and programs, reprinted in: The mind's i," 1981.
- [12] J. L. Pollock, *Cognitive carpentry: A blueprint for how to build a person*. Mit Press, 1995.
- [13] R. W. Picard, *Affective computing*. MIT press, 2000.
- [14] E. Hildt, "Artificial intelligence: Does consciousness matter?" *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 10, p. 1535, 2019.
- [15] T. Nagel, "What is it like to be a bat?" *The philosophical review*, vol. 83, no. 4, pp. 435–450, 1974.
- [16] M. Parks, *Why Shouldn't We Think that Cognition Has Proprietary Phenomenal Character?* University of California, Davis, 2022.
- [17] T. Bayne and M. Montague, *Cognitive phenomenology*. Oxford University Press on Demand, 2011.
- [18] D. Pitt, "Introspection, phenomenality, and the availability of intentional content," *Cognitive phenomenology*, pp. 141–173, 2011.
- [19] M. Montague, *The given: Experience and its content*. Oxford University Press, 2016.
- [20] W. S. Robinson, "Thoughts without distinctive non-imagistic phenomenology," *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research*, vol. 70, no. 3, pp. 534–562, 2005.
- [21] A. A. Mendelovici, *The phenomenal basis of intentionality*. Oxford University Press, 2018.
- [22] D. Pitt, "The phenomenology of cognition or what is it like to think that p?" *Philosophy and phenomenological research*, vol. 69, no. 1, pp. 1–36, 2004.
- [23] P. Carruthers and B. Veillet, "The case against cognitive phenomenology," *Cognitive phenomenology*, pp. 35–56, 2011.
- [24] J. Levine, "On the phenomenology of thought," *Cognitive phenomenology*, vol. 103, 2011.
- [25] M. Parks, "On the self-knowledge argument for cognitive phenomenology," *Journal of Cognition and Neuroethics*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 91–102, 2019.
- [26] J. Schaffer, "What not to multiply without necessity," *Australasian Journal of Philosophy*, vol. 93, no. 4, pp. 644–664, 2015.
- [27] M. N. Keas, "Systematizing the theoretical virtues," *Synthese*, vol. 195, no. 6, pp. 2761–2793, 2018.
- [28] S. S. Sparrow and S. M. Davis, "Recent advances in the assessment of intelligence and cognition," *The Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry and Allied Disciplines*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 117–131, 2000.
- [29] H. Rindermann, D. Becker, and T. R. Coyle, "Survey of expert opinion on intelligence: Causes of international differences in cognitive ability tests," *Frontiers in psychology*, vol. 7, p. 399, 2016.
- [30] A. Clark and D. Chalmers, "The extended mind," *analysis*, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 7–19, 1998.
- [31] B. Sellner, F. W. Heger, L. M. Hiatt, R. Simmons, and S. Singh, "Coordinated multiagent teams and sliding autonomy for large-scale assembly," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 94, no. 7, pp. 1425–1444, 2006.
- [32] P. R. Smart, "Toward a mechanistic account of extended cognition," *Philosophical Psychology*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 1107–1135, 2022.
- [33] C. Allen, "On (not) defining cognition," *Synthese*, vol. 194, no. 11, pp. 4233–4249, 2017.
- [34] M. Spener, "Disagreement about cognitive phenomenology," *Cognitive phenomenology*, pp. 268–284, 2011.
- [35] A. Buccella and A. A. Springler, "Phenomenology: What's ai got to do with it?" *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences*, pp. 1–16, 2022.
- [36] J. Searle, "What your computer can't know," 2014.